

Reaction of rice culture seedlings to thrips

G. Logiswaran, V. Kr. Sathiyandam, K. Ramaraju, and P.C. Sundara Babu, Agricultural Entomology Department, Agricultural College and Research Institute, Madurai 625104, Tamil Nadu, India

We studied the resistance to thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) of four gall midge (GM)-resistant cultures, two GM-susceptible cultures, six cultures with multiple resistance to stem borer, GM, and green leafhopper, and five popular varieties in the nursery during 1986 kharif. Seedlings were screened at 20 d after sowing by the hand sweep method.

GM-susceptible Sona was resistant to thrips; GM-resistant ET8649 was susceptible (see table). Multiple pest-resistant BG367-3 and TM10137 were susceptible to thrips, multiple resistant TM4506 was resistant. CO 43 had the lowest thrips incidence. □

Average number of thrips in the field, Madurai, India.

Culture	Thrips (no.)/ hand sweep
<i>GM-resistant cultures^a</i>	
KT6012 (IR8/W1263)	24
ET6315 (Sona/Manoharsali)	23
IET8649	39
IET8655	21
<i>GM-susceptible cultures^a</i>	
Sona	13
IR20 (IR262/TKM6)	24
CD (P = 0.05)	14
<i>Cultures with multiple insect resistance^b</i>	
BG367-3 (BG280-1-2/Ptb 33)	116
TM10137 (IR26/CR106-190)	92
TM10237 (ADT32/TKM9//IR34)	32
TM4966 (TKM8/ADT9//CR141-192/IR26)	41
TM4506 (Sigadis/CR138-941)	27
TM4300 (IR262/Bhavani)	40
<i>Popular rice varieties^b</i>	
PY3	67
TKM9 (Triveni/CO 39)	44
IR50 (IR2153-14-1-6-2//IR28//IR36)	55
White Ponni (Mutant of Ponni)	42
CO 43 (Dasal/IR20)	39
CD (P = 0.05)	23

^aMean of 4 replications. ^bMean of 3 replications.

Resistance to thrips of traditional rice cultivars

R. Velusamy, K. Natarajamoorthy, G.A. Palanisamy, S. Palanisamy, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

Severe thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) infestation in Jul 1986 killed most high-yielding varieties and breeding lines in the nursery (10-15 d after sowing [DAS]). However, several traditional cultivars resisted thrips damage.

We evaluated 400 traditional and 250 high-yielding rice cultivars for thrips resistance in the field. Pregerminated seed was sown in 3 rows 1 m long in moist soil at 1 seed/cm. Resistant Ptb 33 and susceptible TN1 checks were sown at random. At 7 DAS, the water level was raised. At 15 DAS, when TN1 seedlings were completely wilted, damage was rated on the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale.

All high-yielding cultivars were susceptible to thrips; 39 traditional cultivars were resistant (see table).

Hill rice resistance to leafhoppers and planthoppers in Tamil Nadu

R. Velusamy, G.A. Palanisamy, and K. Natarajamoorthy, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

Traditional rice cultures are grown Aug-Jan under rainfed conditions in the hilly regions of Gudalur, Nilgiris District, Tamil Nadu, at an altitude of 1,342 m, annual rainfall 2,000 mm. Farmers prefer traditional pest-free cultivars that can be raised unprotected.

Seeds of 10 traditional hill rices collected from farmers' fields in Gudalur were evaluated for resistance to leafhoppers and planthoppers in the greenhouse, using the standard

Thrips resistance in traditional rice cultivars.

Cultivar	Origin
Sirumani	Chingleput, Tamil Nadu
Arunjothi	Chingleput, Tamil Nadu
Thattan Samba	Chingleput, Tamil Nadu
Pitchavari	Chingleput, Tamil Nadu
Balavani Samba	Madurai, TN
Sirumanian	Madurai, TN
Uppu milahi	Ramanthapuram, TN
Varagu milahi	Ramanthapuram, TN
Ariyan	Ramanthapuram, TN
Vellai kattai	Ramanthapuram, TN
Red Sirumani	Jhanjavur, TN
Molagolukulu	Jhanjavur, TN
Sadai Thillai	Jhanjavur, TN
Palkachakka	Jhanjavur, TN
Senthilnayagam	Tirunelveli, TN
Mapili Samba	Tirunelveli, TN
Thattai Vellai	Tirunelveli, TN
Valavasa Muntan	Tirunelveli, TN
Veedhi Vadangan	Tirunelveli, TN
Kalmanavari	Tirunelveli, TN
Koola Valai	Tirunelveli, TN
Garudan Samba	South Arcot, TN
Kottamalli Samba	South Arcot, TN
Katta Samba	Trichy, TN
Perumbalam Samba	Trichy, TN
Pattarai Samba	Palur, TN
Annapetta	Malabar, Kerala
Cheera	Malabar, Kerala
Chengaramani	Malabar, Kerala
Chevukuttadan	Malabar, Kerala
Kuruthu Kumblovn	Malabar, Kerala
Kuthi Kondappan	Malabar, Kerala
Kuttadan	Malabar, Kerala
Mundan	Malabar, Kerala
Mundathan	Malabar, Kerala
Moolai Mangalation	Godavari, Andhra Pradesh
Karthigai Samba	Godavari, Andhra Pradesh
Kaki R. Akkulu	Nellore, Andhra Pradesh
Bobbili ganti	Vizakapattinam, Andhra Pradesh

seedbox screening technique. Ptb 33 and TN1 were the resistant and susceptible checks. Separate seedboxes were used for each insect species × cultivar, with five replications. At 7 d after seeding, seedlings were infested with 8 to 10 second-instar nymphs per seedling for brown planthopper (BPH) and whitebacked planthopper (WBPH), and 5 second-instar nymphs per seedling for green leafhopper (GLH). Damage was scored according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale when 95% of TN1 plants were killed.

All 10 traditional cultivars (Chethuvali, Karuvali, Kodagan, Kothandam, Mangalapuram, Maranel, Thodavalan, Valan Channel, Vali, and Velumbala) were highly resistant to BPH, WBPH, and GLH. □